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Simulations and Experiments on the Radiation Resilience of Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT The increasing reliance on Artificial Intelligence (AI) in space exploration necessitates a thorough understanding of its resilience under cosmic conditions. Cosmic radiation can degrade memory, corrupt stored software, and induce bit-flips that impair AI functionality. To address this, we developed a simulation framework that systematically injects bit-flips into different AI architectures to investigate vulnerability to radiation damage across model sizes and storage precisions (32- and 64-bit). The results were validated through gamma irradiation experiments using commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) devices employing SDRAM and EEPROM technology.

Our findings show that certain AI models exhibit remarkable robustness with extensive bit-flips required to significantly degrade the performance. Simple architectures with a large number of weights are particularly suited for radiation-rich environments. Experimental results further reveal a bias toward bit-flips from 1 to 0, but generally pinpoint a notable radiation hardness of COTS devices.

This work advances the practical application of AI in space, medicine, and energy generation by establishing concrete model selection guidelines and an adaptable framework for predicting software response to radiation.

INDEX TERMS Artificial Intelligence, Bit-flip Simulation, Commercial Off-the-Shelf (COTS) Electronics, Gamma Irradiation Damage, Space Applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly embedded in daily life, powering applications from language translation to autonomous navigation. Its integration into critical domains such as space missions, medical treatments, and energy generation is a natural next step. AI models, particularly those based on supervised learning, rely on precise digital representations of learned weights to make predictions and classify new data. The integrity of these models depends directly on the reliability of the underlying hardware.

However, radiation-rich environments expose computing systems to ionizing particles, which can degrade hardware — particularly volatile memory — and thereby corrupt stored or running software. Understanding how such effects impact AI performance is essential for safely deploying these systems in space and other high-radiation settings. Cosmic radiation [1], composed of high-energy particles originating from the Sun and beyond the solar system, can induce various types

of damage. In this study, we focus on bit-flips in digital memory [2], where data are stored as binary numbers (ones and zeros). Memory cells may transiently or permanently change their logical state, potentially corrupting the weights of AI models and degrading performance.

High-performance hardware, often based on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components, is especially attractive for AI deployment due to its availability and computational capability. Radiation-hardened space-grade hardware, in contrast, is costly and limited in performance. Recent work has examined the radiation hardness of COTS devices such as the NVIDIA Jetson under proton and heavy-ion exposure [3], [4]. Other studies have explored experimental and simulation-based approaches to investigate single-event upsets (SEUs) and bit-flips in AI systems [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. Yet, no prior study has systematically considered the impact of individual bit positions, device- and component-level experiments, different radiation types — particularly gamma rays — or variations in

AI architectures, model sizes, and data storage formats (32- and 64-bit).

Thus, there is a need for an universal, adaptable simulation framework, validated by experiment, to inject radiation-induced bit-flips into software and evaluate the vulnerability and robustness of AI models under varying conditions. Such a tool can guide the selection of architectures optimized for radiation-rich environments. The present work addresses this gap in the context of the ISS experiment PK-4 [10] by combining controlled bit-flip simulations with gamma irradiation experiments on COTS devices, providing both methodological advancements and practical recommendations for AI deployment in challenging radiation environments.

II. METHODS

We employed a two-pronged methodology to assess AI robustness under radiation-induced bit-flips. First, a simulation framework was developed to inject controlled bit-flips into AI model parameters, allowing low-cost evaluation of worst-case scenarios, flexible modeling of specific environments, and rapid testing of diverse architectures. Second, irradiation experiments on COTS devices provided physical validation of simulation predictions under realistic exposure conditions. The combination of simulation flexibility and experimental realism enables both comprehensive exploration and empirical verification of AI behavior in radiation-rich settings.

A. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

The simulation framework was designed to systematically introduce bit-flips into AI model parameters and evaluate the resulting impact on performance. Several model architectures were implemented, covering a range of complexities and parameter counts to reflect different computational demands and storage requirements. Models were stored in both 32-bit and 64-bit floating-point formats, according to the IEEE754 standard [11], to capture the influence of numerical representation on radiation susceptibility.

For the simulation, the Python version 3 [12] and the libraries `numpy`, `matplotlib`, `pandas`, `scipy`, `tensorflow`, `random`, `os`, and `struct` were used. The model weights are saved after the training as decimal numbers. To inject bit-flips, the weights values were converted into 32- and 64-bit binary numbers, for example $w_{dec} = 0.044257015$ into $w_{bin} = 00111101001101010100011011011000$. Then, one bit is flipped, for example Bit 7 from 0 to 1 (in MSB1 bit numbering, where the most significant bit on the left side is labeled as Bit 1 to enhance comparisons between storage formats). This manipulated binary number is converted back into decimal. This resulting weight value $w_{new} = 0.70811224$ is passed to the network and the performance is observed. The Python implementation is shown in Fig. 1. The performance of the classification [13] can be measured as:

$$\text{accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 1. Activity diagram for the manipulation of a weight to introduce bit-flips. The random number is in the range of 32 or 64, depending on the used storage format.

In this equation, TP and TN represent true positive and negative. FP and FN represent false true and negative. The framework allows control over the number, location, and distribution of flipped bits, enabling both random injections and targeted modifications at specific bit positions. Each corrupted model was evaluated with a ground truth weight set and on the same validation dataset used for baseline performance to enable comparisons between the manipulations. The modular design of the simulation permits flexible modeling of diverse operating conditions, supports reproducibility, and enables rapid exploration of worst-case scenarios across multiple AI architectures. The variation parameters to identify an optimum are model sizes and architecture complexities, storage precisions (32- and 64-bit), and bit positions.

1) Architecture Selection

To assess the influence of network design on radiation robustness, two AI architectures of varying size and complexity were selected for evaluation, which can be seen in Fig. 2. The first network investigated is a very simple Multi-Layer-Perceptron (MLP) [14]. It consists of an input layer, hidden layer, and output layer with a total of 78,500 kernel weights. The second network is the compact U-Net for AIPEX [15] [16], which is a more complex and deep network with several layers. It is a convolutional neural network (CNN) and consists of 25 layers, of which 15 are convolutional layer containing a total of 9296 kernel weights. Bias weights are not considered at this stage.

The difference is that the MLP concentrates many weights in few layers, while the U-Net distributes fewer weights across many layers. This leads to more complexity and additionally requires a layer-wise approach. Both networks can have floating point weight values in the range -1 to 1.

To investigate different storage precisions, the MLP was manipulated in 32-bit and 64-bit storage format, and the U-Net was manipulated in 64-bit storage format. This enables powerful comparisons.

2) Bit Manipulation Strategy

We studied the influence of bit positions and weight quantities affected to approach this problem systematically. In any case, each bit of the 32 or 64 bits was manipulated in the binary representation of a weight value for certain weight quantities. In the MLP, the numbers of manipulated weights are determined by the number of weights per neuron, and the weights are chosen randomly. For the U-Net, the manipulations are spread uniformly across the layers and randomly within one layer. This means that when we manipulated 10 % of the total weights, 10 % were manipulated in each layer, and these weights of one layer were selected and distributed randomly. There is no preferred direction for $1 \rightarrow 0$ or $0 \rightarrow 1$ flips. The flip direction depends on the value of the randomly chosen bit and is thus also random. Additionally, a layer-wise manipulation was performed for the U-Net to investigate the influence of each single layer on the overall performance. To ensure comparability, the decimal value 1 was added to every weight

FIGURE 2. Architecture of the MLP (top) and U-Net (down, [15]). The convolutional layers of the U-Net, which contain the weights, are displayed in dark blue.

in the investigated layer, creating an intentionally problematic weight value. This manipulation was applied to one layer at a time.

These randomized distributions and theoretical quantities are limiting the work and make practical constraints and an experimental verification necessary.

The resulting performance values for each manipulation setup are the output of the simulation. These data were analyzed using Python and visualized with matplotlib. The plots allowed for direct comparisons between storage precisions and model types. In addition, the results of the MLP and U-Net were normalized to enable relative comparisons to account for different numbers of weights in the architectures and for different initial performance values. For both networks, the manipulation of 10 % of the weights was considered. The resulting relative performance change after flipping each bit was obtained with

$$\Delta\text{performance} = 100\% - \frac{\text{performance}_{\text{actual}}}{\text{performance}_{\text{original}}} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

and compared through $\Delta\text{performance}_{\text{U-Net}} - \Delta\text{performance}_{\text{MLP}}$.

B. IRRADIATION EXPERIMENTS

To complement the simulations with experimental validation under realistic space conditions, irradiation tests were carried out both at the component level and at the device level. This dual approach allowed us to investigate isolated memory units without secondary effects from other components, as well as complete COTS devices in their operational configura-

tion. The hardware under test included synchronous dynamic random access memory (SDRAM) and Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memory (EEPROM) modules representative of common memory technologies in AI systems. EEPROM stores data in floating-gate transistors, where charge is trapped or removed to represent binary states. The stored information is non-volatile, meaning it is retained even without power. SDRAM stores each bit as charge on a capacitor that must be periodically refreshed due to leakage. Access is synchronized with the system clock, enabling high-speed, volatile data storage for active computations. By testing both EEPROM and SDRAM, we capture the radiation response of non-volatile charge storage as well as volatile capacitor-based memory, thereby covering the two fundamental modes of data retention in AI hardware.

The device-level tests were conducted on a NVIDIA Jetson Nano 10-1-A0 board [17], which relies on SDRAM (4 GB 64-bit LPDDR4 1600MHz - 25.6 GB/s). The goal for the tests with the Jetson board is to test volatile memory with a RAM-Check. To do so, the perfectly alternating bit pattern 0x55 is frequently completely inverted to pattern 0xAA so that every memory cell has to change its value. If some cells cannot change their value anymore due to damage, mismatches from expected pattern can be counted. Additionally, non volatile memory of the Jetson is tested by saving U-Net weights in the internal storage (16 GB eMMC 5.1 Flash) and making frequent backups of current state to enable comparisons.

The component-level tests were performed with EEPROMs of the type 24AA64/24LC64 [18]. To study both, operational vulnerability and unbiased susceptibility, the EEPROMs were irradiated in three distinct groups:

- **Unbiased group** (24 units): No electrical connections during exposure.
- **Read-only group** (4 units): Live readout during irradiation via Raspberry Pi.
- **Active write cycle group** (4 units): Full write/erase/read cycles during irradiation.

Additionally, there is an unirradiated control group (8 units). The EEPROMs are tested with and without active operation. Devices in the unbiased and read-only groups were prefilled with the static bit pattern 0x55, whereas the write-cycle group was subjected to alternating patterns, analogous to those used in the RAM check. Care is taken to ensure the EEPROMs do not reach their endurance limit of 1,000,000 write cycles per cell to avoid corrupting the results.

The chosen hardware and AI models widely used. So far, only these types of devices have been considered, which already feature a lot of important aspects but could still be complemented with other device tests. This experimental design allows cross-correlation between volatile and non-volatile memory responses by irradiating a device containing both memory types and stand-alone non-volatile memories tested under permanent storage conditions as well as under RAM-like operating conditions.

1) Irradiation Source and Dosimetry

Irradiation was performed using a Co-60 gamma source at the Strahlenzentrum Gießen. The dose rate was 6 Gy/h, and samples were exposed for a total of 50 h, resulting in an accumulated dose of 300 Gy. This dose was chosen to simulate a high-radiation environment and to test the robustness of AI hardware under conditions exceeding typical operational exposure, enabling evaluation of worst-case bit-flip scenarios. The accumulated dose was chosen based on constraints from previous literature ([19] on EEPROMs and [4] on the Jetson board) and the availability of the radiation source. For comparison, during a 10-year ISS mission, the devices are exposed to an accumulated dose of only 2.92 Gy [20]. This study currently only considers gamma radiation and no other types of radiation.

2) Experimental Setup

The irradiation campaign was performed with a combined setup allowing simultaneous exposure of the Jetson board and EEPROM groups (Fig. 3). To facilitate controlled EEPROM testing under distinct operating conditions, a custom printed circuit board (PCB) was designed in Altium Designer [21]. The schematic is shown in Fig. 4. The board provides dedicated power rails, I²C communication lines (SDA and SCL), and careful separation of the three EEPROM groups (unbiased, passively read, and actively cycled) to avoid cross-influence during irradiation. The read and write groups are interfaced to a Raspberry Pi controller via the I²C protocol [22], with proper signal routing and 4.7 k Ω pull-up resistors to ensure integrity. Address pins (A0–A2) of the EEPROMs were configured to access devices at Raspberry Pi addresses 0x50–0x57, following standard binary addressing.

Both the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson were connected to a Linux notebook via Ethernet. This allowed remote execution of monitoring scripts, initiation of test routines, and live observation of output data during irradiation. On the Jetson, a Python script was running to perform the RAM-check and non-volatile memory test (see Fig. 5) and on the Raspberry Pi a C++ script was running to perform the read and write operations on the EEPROMs (see Fig. 6). Logging was performed on external hard drives and over the network to ensure redundancy.

To protect control electronics and storage media, the Raspberry Pi and hard drives were placed behind a 15 cm lead shield. Based on the exponential attenuation law, this corresponds to an exposure of only $\approx 3 \times 10^{-4}$ of the unshielded intensity, i.e. a reduction by more than four orders of magnitude.

FIGURE 3. Schematic overview of the setup at irradiation center. In the radiation chamber, 8 EEPROMs connected to a Raspberry Pi, 24 unbiased EEPROMs, and the Jetson Nano 10-1-A0 are exposed to gamma irradiation. The monitoring with a laptop is performed outside the chamber, shielded by thick concrete walls. The devices are connected via ethernet.

FIGURE 4. Circuit schematic of the custom EEPROM test board.

FIGURE 5. Activity diagram of RAM-check (alternating bit patterns 0xAA and 0x55) and weight-backup code for irradiation of the Jetson Nano board.

FIGURE 6. Activity diagram of EEPROM code implemented on a Raspberry Pi. Devices 0x50 - 0x53 are the active write cycle group with alternating patterns (0xAA and 0x55) and devices 0x54 - 0x57 are the read-only group. For the unbiased group, only the initial write operation is performed before the experiment and a final read operation after the experiment.

3) Test Procedure

To perform the experiments, the devices were positioned directly in front of the gamma source. The Jetson was placed in a standard desktop orientation, while the EEPROMs were mounted upright to maximize the exposed area. A network connection was established between the Linux PC, the Jetson, and the Raspberry Pi, and the monitoring scripts were launched. The setup was then irradiated for 50 h. Throughout the exposure, the experiment could be monitored from the laptop: the terminal displayed the current status of the Jetson RAM check as well as the expected patterns and mismatch counts for the EEPROMs. After irradiation, all devices were shut down cleanly, and the logged data were analyzed. For both the Jetson and EEPROMs, mismatch counts were evaluated first; if anomalies were detected, the detailed read patterns were further examined using Python scripts. For further analysis, a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was performed with `scipy.fft`. Additionally, a Weibull function of the following form was used:

$$\sigma(D) = \sigma_{\text{sat}} \cdot \left(1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{D - D_0}{W} \right)^s \right] \right), \quad D > D_0 \quad (3)$$

and a simplified Mean-Fluence-to-Failure (MFTF) model:

$$p(\Phi) = 1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\Phi}{\eta} \right) \quad (4)$$

to extract physically interpretable parameters regarding failure onset. In the equations, $\sigma(D)$ is the cumulative mismatch count at dose D (in Gy), σ_{sat} is the saturation mismatch count, D_0 is the threshold dose at which mismatches begin to appear, W is a width parameter that describes the dose range over which degradation occurs, and s is a shape parameter indicating the steepness of the failure onset, p is the observed failure fraction, Φ is the total applied dose, η is the characteristic fluence (the dose at which 63.2% of devices fail), and $\sigma_{\text{device}} = 1/\eta$ is the effective device-level cross section [23], [24]. The MFTF model assumes negligible high-dose effects, consistent with the dose range considered in this study.

In contrast to the simulation, a few potential error sources exist in the experiments. Non-memory components may fail, leading to complete device malfunction with ambiguous causes. The spatial arrangement around the source could result in different accumulated doses and charge levels across devices. Device orientation may also influence sensitivity, but only one configuration was tested. Finally, uncertainties in calculating the absorbed dose cannot be excluded.

III. RESULTS

This section reports the outcomes of the simulation framework and irradiation experiments. The simulations quantify the effects of radiation-induced bit flips systematically, while the experiments provide physical validation with COTS devices. Together, these complementary results enable a comprehensive assessment of AI robustness against radiation-induced errors.

A. SIMULATION

The simulation results reveal how model architecture, storage precision, and bit-flip characteristics influence performance, allowing systematic comparisons to identify configurations best suited for radiation-rich environments.

1) Bit-Flip Effects on Decimal Number

Fig. 7 illustrates how flipping individual bits in 32-bit and 64-bit binary representations affects the decimal value. As example, an MLP weight value was randomly chosen for demonstration. In these storage formats, the first bit always determines the sign of the decimal number. In 32-bit, the following 8 bits are responsible for the exponent and the last 23 bits for the mantissa. In 64-bit (double precision), 11 bits are responsible for exponent and 52 for mantissa. Flips in the exponent-bits can cause very drastic deviations in the order of several magnitudes, while flips in the mantissa-bits cause only slight deviations in the order of a few percents. Flipping the first bit inverts the sign leading to $\pm 200\%$ deviation.

The plots show that higher deviations are possible in 64-bit format, particularly for Bit 2. Beyond, the curves follow a similar behavior and the 64-bit format includes a much higher quantity of bits with negligible impact on the decimal value (see also Tab. 1 for more details). Thus, the 64-bit format offers an overall lower probability for significant damage for randomly distributed bit-flips.

2) Comparison of Storage Formats

The top and middle panels in Fig. 8 show the results of the MLP in 32-bit and 64-bit storage formats. According to Eq. 1, a performance value of 1 corresponds to perfect classification, whereas a value of 0 indicates poor classification. The performance plots mirror the resulting decimal values in Fig. 7, displaying similar features but in inverted form, and they reflect the trend that Bit 2 can cause the most significant deviations when it flips from 0 to 1. The remainder of the curves follow the same trend with a little offset. The following bits can cause minor changes, with a second prominent peak at Bit 7 (32-bit) and Bit 10 (64-bit). The star markers indicate that there are no more changes in the performance value from Bit 14 (32-bit) and Bit 19 (64-bit) onward. This means that in the 32-bit format, 18 bit positions do not deteriorate performance, whereas in the 64-bit format, 45 such positions exist — a substantially larger proportion. Although the two prominent performance troughs are slightly more pronounced in the 64-bit case, the format is likely to be more resilient overall, since the probability of a randomly flipped bit degrading performance is lower. Less common storage formats, such as 16-bit, are not considered in this study, but the observed trend indicates that higher-precision formats may offer improved resilience.

FIGURE 7. Influence of each bit on the decimal value when it flips for 32-bit format (top) and 64-bit format (bottom) for the example weight value 0.044257015.

FIGURE 8. Development of performance after flipping each bit for different quantities of weights for the MLP in 32-bit format (top), 64-bit format (middle), and U-Net in 64-bit format (bottom). The asterisk marks the point where the performance remains constant.

3) Comparison of Model Sizes

The middle and bottom panels in Fig. 8 show the results of both the MLP and U-Net in 64-bit format each. These plots differ in a number of important ways. The U-Net exhibits substantially greater fluctuations at the first bit positions compared to the MLP. Its performance repeatedly drops to zero, a behavior not observed for the MLP. Moreover, fluctuations persist up to bit position 25 in the U-Net, meaning that fewer bits have negligible impact and the probability that a random flip causes damage is correspondingly higher.

The MLP contains substantially more weights than the U-Net. Thus, in absolute comparison, the same amount of manipulations with specific bit-flips will lead to more drastic changes in the U-Net than in the MLP, as visible in Fig. 8. Therefore, in relative comparison, the same percentages of weights in both networks and relative performance deviations (according to Eq. 2) were considered. Results show that performance deviations are identical for 44 manipulated bit positions, while the U-Net performs marginally better ($\approx 0.1\%$) for 5 bit positions, and the MLP performs meaningfully better (by up to 70%) for 14 bit positions (see Tab. 2).

These observations imply that the U-Net's response to radiation-induced bit-flips is way more complex. To further investigate susceptibility to altered weights, failures were simulated on a layer-by-layer basis. The results show that most layers, when corrupted, caused a complete collapse of performance, while only the first layer retained partial functionality. This suggests that the U-Net's architecture is particularly vulnerable to localized faults in deeper layers, where errors propagate more strongly through the network. Such vulnerability likely arises from its complex and deep structure, in which different layers have distinct functions and weight quantities, making faults in certain parts of the model disproportionately harmful. This also highlights the risk that errors in a specific memory area or neighboring memory cells could lead to significant performance degradation.

The observed performance fluctuations make the U-Net less reliable in radiation-rich environments, leading to the suggestion to prefer simple architectures like the MLP for space applications.

B. EXPERIMENTS

The irradiation experiments provide empirical validation of the simulation results and offer direct insight into the behavior of COTS devices under sustained gamma exposure. The tests were performed on device level (with the Jetson Nano board) and on component level (with EEPROMs).

1) Jetson Platform

The irradiation of the Jetson board revealed no mismatches in either volatile or non-volatile memory throughout the full exposure up to a total dose of 300 Gy. Both the RAM-check routine and the weight backup procedure showed consistent performance, indicating that the device maintained data integrity under gamma irradiation.

The only observable effect was a USB port malfunction after

an accumulated dose of approximately 9 Gy, which limited peripheral connectivity but did not compromise the main system operation. The device could still be accessed remotely via the network. This isolated failure suggests that peripheral interfaces may be more sensitive to radiation than the core computing elements.

Overall, the Jetson demonstrated high radiation hardness, with memory operations remaining unaffected under the given experimental conditions. These findings support the suitability of COTS AI hardware for deployment in radiation-rich environments, although interface reliability and potential delayed effects should be considered in mission design.

2) EEPROMs

In contrast to the Jetson results, the EEPROMs exhibited clear differences between operational modes, with no mismatches observed in the unbiased and read-only groups, but notable errors occurring during active write cycles. The mismatch count during the irradiation time for the devices of the write cycle group is shown in Fig. 9. Each EEPROM has a storage capacity of 8192 bytes, and during irradiation every byte eventually experienced an upset, corresponding to a per-byte SEU (single-event upset) cross section of 1. To characterize and quantify the response to radiation, the Weibull distribution (Eq. 3) was employed to model the evolution of mismatches as a function of total dose. This analysis yielded threshold doses of 192.54, 187.30, 182.36, and 195.90 Gy for the four devices of the write-cycle group. While the devices did not register their first faults simultaneously, the onset occurred within a narrow dose window. The Weibull parameters further indicate that the transition spans approximately 2 Gy, with all devices exhibiting a comparably sharp rise in errors (see Tab. 3). Using a simplified MFTF model (Eq. 4), the statistic characteristic fluence at which devices may begin to fail was extrapolated for the two remaining functional groups. It predicts that the read-only group might start to fail at 288.5 Gy and the unbiased group at 1520.2 Gy. These results align closely with previous findings [19], and suggest that additional malfunctions would likely emerge under slightly extended irradiation. Unbiased devices are exceptionally robust and require very high accumulated doses before failure. Additionally, the spatial distribution of errors within the memory array was examined by summing all mismatches occurring in each memory byte and plotting the cumulative mismatch count per byte index. The results, shown in Fig. 10, indicate that mismatches are generally evenly distributed across the array, although small regular fluctuations in the flip count are visible. Closer inspection, supported by an FFT analysis, reveals a 64-byte periodicity.

To further investigate the byte-specific behavior, the different amounts of cumulative mismatches were examined for the Bytes 4286 (representing the lower plateau of the distribution, Fig. 10) and 4288 (higher plateau). Each byte comprises eight bits, and we consistently observed that exactly four bits flipped in every byte. The results show that four bits flip within a short time and for the remaining duration, the

byte keeps its 4 mismatches. That means that the cumulative mismatch count per byte rises linearly, since each iteration adds these fixed four mismatches. Additionally, we found out that Byte 4286 experienced the first mismatches almost 1000 s later than Byte 4288. This is the reason for the upper and lower plateaus in the plot: the summation of mismatches ends for all bytes at the same time, but for some bytes it started earlier. They were damaged earlier, reached their saturation earlier, kept the saturation value over time, and accumulated a higher mismatch count. The 64 byte periodicity gives an interesting hint which bytes are more or less susceptible to radiation damage and degrade earlier or later. This suggests location-dependent sensitivity within the memory device — an important observation for radiation tolerance studies or identifying weak memory cells.

Beyond the device- and byte-level characterization, individual bit behavior was analyzed to explore the nature of the underlying errors and to explain why each byte experienced only 4 flips. All observed bit-flips occurred exclusively in the $1 \rightarrow 0$ direction, which aligns with expectations for EEPROM memory. In such devices, the logical '1' state typically represents a charged floating gate, and cumulative write cycles involving high electric fields leave the cells more vulnerable to radiation-induced charge loss. Ionizing radiation can accelerate charge leakage through radiation-enhanced tunneling or trap generation, promoting a transition from '1' to '0' [25]. This directionality also explains why 4 bit-flips per byte are observed, since 4 ones can flip to zero and the 4 zeros remain constant.

The research conducted by [26] and [27] supports the hypotheses of bit-flip directionality and aligns with our findings. [28] even reports about a dominance of $1 \rightarrow 0$ flips in other memory devices.

A deeper understanding of the observed bit-flip directionality would require detailed knowledge of the internal structure and charge storage mechanisms of the specific EEPROMs used, which is not publicly available. However, the consistent $1 \rightarrow 0$ transitions observed across all devices highlight a clear and reproducible effect. Investigating the physical origins and technological dependencies of such directional behavior presents an interesting and relevant avenue for future research in radiation-hardened non-volatile memory design.

Finally, we observed that the damaged EEPROMs of the write-cycle group annealed after three weeks at room temperature, restoring full functionality in all devices. The high radiation tolerance and the annealing behavior underscore the ability of memory components to withstand harsh environmental conditions and maintain reliable operation in space.

IV. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

This study represents a critical step toward understanding the resilience of AI in radiation-rich environments. While the demand for AI in space missions, medical treatments, and energy systems is growing, its reliability under ionizing radiation has remained uncertain. To address this, we combined targeted simulations with gamma irradiation experiments on

FIGURE 9. Mismatch count over time during irradiation for the devices of the active write-cycle group. They reach the saturation at 8192 mismatches, which corresponds to the total number of bytes per EEPROM. The right panel shows a zoom on x scale.

COTS devices.

The findings indicate that certain AI models can generally withstand radiation-induced bit-flips, with substantial corruption required to significantly impair performance. Simulations identified a particularly vulnerable case — a $0 \rightarrow 1$ flip at Bit 2 — that would cause major performance degradation. Experiments, however, showed only $1 \rightarrow 0$ flips, ruling out this worst-case scenario and thereby reinforcing the conclusion that COTS devices exhibit strong radiation tolerance. Both results point to a high intrinsic robustness of AI against random faults in volatile and non-volatile memory. As a potential design guideline, storage schemes that favor more zeros than ones may reduce the risk of unexpected bit-flip effects. Experiments also demonstrate that temporarily powering down electronics during radiation events effectively mitigates radiation-induced errors.

The combined simulation and irradiation results provide a coherent view of AI resilience under radiation. The EEPROM experiments confirm the random spatial distribution of bit-flips assumed in the simulations, reinforcing their validity. The interplay between device-level testing, component analysis, and simulation proved particularly fruitful, as each approach complements the others, simultaneously highlighting

FIGURE 10. Integral mismatch count plotted over byte index revealing the spatial distribution of mismatches. The right panel shows a zoom on x scale which reveals the 64-byte periodicity.

device robustness, potential component failure mechanisms, and simulation-based predictions, while providing insight into both volatile and non-volatile memory. This integrated methodology represents a significant step toward a unified understanding of radiation effects across hardware and software. However, future research should extend this work by refining the simulation framework to account for directional flip tendencies and bias weights, exploring additional AI architectures, and conduct additional irradiation tests with diverse devices and radiation types. Understanding detailed device-level failure mechanisms, as well as evaluating shielding and mitigation strategies, including device orientation and layout optimization to minimize radiation exposure, will be important next steps.

From an application perspective, the results suggest that relatively simple architectures with many weights in a few layers, such as MLPs, are preferable in radiation-rich environments. More broadly, they demonstrate that non-radiation-hardened high-performance hardware can, in many cases, be safely employed in space applications.

The simulation and experimental approaches developed here provide an adaptable toolkit for evaluating the radiation hardness of diverse software and hardware systems. This adaptability opens the door to cost-efficient hardware solutions not only for space missions — such as satellites, telescopes, and interplanetary probes — but also for radiation-intensive fields, making them truly accessible for everyone. Ultimately, this work shows that AI, supported by systematic testing, can become a reliable component of modern infrastructure even in the most challenging environments.

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- **Author contribution:** SP wrote the paper, developed the simulation, designed and conducted the experiments, and analyzed the data. KTB, MSch, and MHT supervised the work. ND developed the AI networks. MK selected the hardware. MPe supported developing the EEPROM scripts. HGZ, MSa, MSt, and MPI supported the development of the experiment.
- **Use of AI:** ChatGPT was used for minor language editing and LaTeX formatting support.
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APPENDIX A EXTENDED DATA

TABLE 1. Excerpt of Resulting Decimal Numbers After Bit-Flips

Flipped bit	32-bit storage format	64-bit storage format
1	-4.42570e-02	-4.42570e-02
2	1.50599e+37	7.95605e+306
3	2.39918e-21	3.30084e-156
4	1.03044e-11	3.82211e-79
5	6.75308e-07	1.30060e-40
6	1.72879e-04	2.39918e-21
7	7.08112e-01	1.03044e-11
8	1.10643e-02	6.75308e-07
9	8.85140e-02	1.72879e-04
10	5.98820e-02	7.08112e-01
11	3.64445e-02	1.10643e-02
12	4.03508e-02	8.85140e-02
13	4.62101e-02	5.98820e-02
14	4.32805e-02	3.64445e-02
15	4.47453e-02	4.03508e-02
16	4.40129e-02	4.62101e-02
17	4.43791e-02	4.32805e-02
18	4.41960e-02	4.47453e-02
19	4.42875e-02	4.40129e-02
20	4.42723e-02	4.43791e-02

Excerpt showing the resulting decimal values after bit-flips in the first 20 bit positions in 32-bit and 64-bit storage formats. The original value without bit-flips is 0.044257015. Bits beyond this range are omitted because their impact becomes negligible.

TABLE 2. Relative Performance Deviations for U-Net and MLP

Bit	$\Delta\text{performance}_{\text{MLP}}$ in %	$\Delta\text{performance}_{\text{U-Net}}$ in %	$\Delta\text{perf}_{\text{U-Net}} - \Delta\text{perf}_{\text{MLP}}$
1	68.4910494557563	100.0	31.5089505442437
2	89.9744250347064	100.0	10.0255749652936
3	24.6240410436050	23.4684924465503	-1.15554859705470
4	29.9335068280702	57.1545841285955	27.2210773005253
5	5.11509062131454	74.5142074281481	69.3991168068336
6	4.53197122952459	29.2715151790289	24.7395439495044
7	6.56777926025485	69.7890631233301	63.2212838630752
8	2.72122789346092	53.2774671442072	50.5562392507463
9	14.4450130852772	67.0624604884968	52.6174474032197
10	62.0460374680582	100.0	37.9539625319418
11	8.99233151962450	100.0	91.0076684803755
12	1.73913239663899	5.17651883959049	3.43738644295149
13	0.48081892084925	8.73323969887156	8.25242077802231
14	0.06138516069382	0.88487264555816	0.82348748486434
15	0.04092140790863	10.4827731207801	10.4418517128715
16	-0.02045765512344	-0.61810427505034	-0.59764661992691
17	0.01023187639259	0.0	-0.01023187639259
18	0.0	-0.80911256331002	-0.80911256331002
19	0.01023187639259	0.0	-0.01023187639259
20	0.0	0.0	0.0

Percentage performance deviations according to Eq. 2 for manipulated weights with 10% bit-flips. Positive values in the last column indicate a larger performance degradation for the U-Net, while negative values indicate a larger degradation for the MLP.

TABLE 3. Fitted Weibull Parameters and Estimated SEU Cross Sections

Device	σ_{sat} (errors)	D_0 (Gy)	W (Gy)	s	σ_{byte} (errors/Gy/byte)
0x50	8192.71	192.54	1.85	3.04	1.00
0x51	8191.24	187.30	5.26	10.56	1.00
0x52	8192.86	182.36	1.63	2.43	1.00
0x53	8191.63	195.90	1.15	3.70	1.00

Fitted Weibull parameters and estimated per-byte SEU cross sections obtained from Eq. 3.

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